

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIVEMENT

this certificate is proudly presented to

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Qurbanov Jasurbek Suvon o'g'li

FERMENTLAR BIOKIMYOSI

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

zenodo

2022-NOYABR

